

Synthesis and Evaluation of Sulphonylhydrazones of Phthalimido Acetaldehyde as Anticancer Agents

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Arylsulphonylhydrazones of 2-pyridinecarboxaldehyde-1-oxide and related compounds possess wide-spectrum antitumor activity¹ in some experimental tumor systems. Earlier reports² from this laboratory described marginal to moderate *in vivo* activity of some arylsulphonylhydrazones of substituted benzaldehydes and nitrosalicylaldehydes in murine Ehrlich Ascites Carcinoma (EAC). Literature survey further reveals³ that different functionalities have been incorporated in the phthalimido molecule used as the carrier and the synthesised compounds obtained thereby show interesting anticancer activities. Recently we have also described⁴ the highly significant anticancer activity of phthalmustine which contain the basic nitrogen mustard antitumor functionality embedded in the phthalimido moiety.

Phthalmustine

Thus phthalimido derivatives containing the aforesaid sulphonylhydrazone functionality may have synergistic cytotoxic activity. However, the anticancer potential of such compounds has not yet been reported in the literature to our knowledge. This led us to prepare and evaluate such compounds (**1a-j**) as a part of our ongoing anticancer drug development programme⁵.

1a; R = 4-CH₃Ph
b; R = 4-BrPh
c; R = 4-ClPh
d; R = 4-FPh
e; R = 4-OCH₃Ph

1f; R = 3,4-diOCH₃Ph
g; R = 4-NHAcPh
h; R = 3-NO₂Ph
i; R = 2-Naphthyl
j; R = CH₃

Results and Discussion

The *in vitro* screening results in the human tumor cell lines showed that none of the compounds has reached the criteria of tumor specificity. Under *in vitro* assay conditions, exposure to an antitumor compound may decrease the number of viable tumor cells by direct cell killing (lysis) or by simply decreasing the rate of proliferation. Apparently under this experimental condition, the compounds did not generate reactive species leading to such cytotoxicity.

The *in vitro* study on the viability of EAC cells showed that one of the compounds (**1d**) had marginal effect (dead cells 41%) at the concentration of 2.0 $\mu\text{mol ml}^{-1}$ compared to control (dead cells 1%). Under similar experimental conditions and concentrations, phthalmustine⁴ and cypenhydramustine⁵ used as the positive controls showed significantly good (dead cells 70%) and excellent (dead cells 98%) effects respectively. Further, the compounds were found to be devoid of anti-HIV activity at NCI.

Experimental

M.p.s. were determined on a Thomas-Hoover Unimelt apparatus and are uncorrected. Ir (nujol), electronic (MeOH) and pmr (DMSO-d₆) spectra were recorded respectively on Perkin-Elmer 377 spectrophotometer, Hitachi 200-20 spectrophotometer and Zeol FX-100 spectrometer (using TMS as internal standard). The purity of the compounds was checked with a Waters HPLC system (solvent delivery model 501; μ -bondapak C₁₈ steel column, 30 cm \times 3.9 mm; isocratic mobile phase acetonitrile-water in varying proportions; flow rate, 1.0 ml min⁻¹; uv detection in M 481 at 220 nm). Satisfactory analytical data were obtained for the compounds.

Phthalimido acetaldehyde was prepared with some modification of the literature procedure⁶. A mixture of phthalic anhydride (1 g, 0.0068 mol) and aminoacetaldehyde diethyl acetal (0.98 ml, 0.0068 mol) was heated at 120° for 1 h with stirring, then cooled and worked up in EtOAc. The resultant mixture was chromatographed over a silica gel column (60–120 mesh). Elution of the column with ether-light petroleum (5%, v/v) afforded *N*-(2,2-diethoxyethyl)-phthalimide as a white crystalline solid (1.36 g, 78%; m.p.

72–73°) which was used directly for the next step. The diethoxy compound (0.5 g) was treated with 2 N HCl (3.5 ml) and the mixture was heated at 100° with stirring for 45–60 min. The resultant clear solution was then kept at 4° overnight. The separated solid was washed with cold water, dried under reduced pressure and crystallised (chloroform-light petroleum ether, 40–60°) to get phthalimido-acetaldehyde as white needles (0.28 g, 78%), m.p. 111–12° (lit.⁶).

Alkyl and arylsulphonylhydrazides were prepared from the corresponding sulphonyl chloride derivatives by treating with hydrazine hydrate according to the literature methods⁷. The m.ps. of RSO₂NHNH₂ were as follows: R = 4-CH₃Ph, 104–07°; 4-BrPh, 117–18°; 4-ClPh, 113–14°; 4-FPh, 87–88°; 4-OCH₃Ph, 110–11°; 3,4-diOCH₃Ph, 139–40°; 4-NHAcPh, 188–92°; 3-NO₂Ph, 125–29°; 2-naphthyl, 137–38°; CH₃, 42–45°.

The sulphonylhydrazones. General method: The appropriate sulphonylhydrazide (5 mmol) was dissolved in ethanol (4–8 ml) by warming at 50–60° and then added to a solution of equimolar amount of phthalimido acetaldehyde in ethanol (4 ml). Since 4-acetylaminophenylsulphonylhydrazide was insoluble in ethanol, tetrahydrofuran was used as the solvent for carrying out the reaction with phthalimido acetaldehyde. The reaction mixture was warmed at 70° for 30 min and then concentrated to half of its volume by distillation of the solvent. After cooling to 0°, the sulphonylhydrazones were crystallised from ethanol; the reaction between 3,4-dimethoxyphenylsulphonylhydrazide and phthalimido acetaldehyde took place at room temperature: **1a** (69%), m.p. 165–67°; ν_{\max} 3420, 3380, 1770, 1705, 1600 cm⁻¹; δ 2.36 (3H, s, CH₃), 4.31 (2H, d, CH₂), 7.12–7.68 (5H, m, CH and ArH), 7.84–8.16 (4H, m, ArH), 11.16 (1H, s, NH); **b** (77%), 171–72°; ν_{\max} 3225, 1775, 1725, 1575 cm⁻¹; δ 4.3 (2H, d, CH₂), 7.3 (1H, t, CH), 7.4 (2H, d, ArH), 7.66 (2H, d, ArH), 7.8–8.08 (4H, m, ArH), 11.34 (1H, s, NH); **c** (65%), 172–74°; ν_{\max} 3220, 1770, 1725 cm⁻¹; δ 4.32 (2H, d, CH₂), 7.32 (1H, t, CH), 7.52–7.84 (4H, m, ArH), 7.9–8.16 (4H, m, ArH), 11.36 (1H, br s, NH); **d** (67%), 170–73°; ν_{\max} 3130, 1770, 1715, 1595 cm⁻¹; δ 4.31 (2H, d, CH₂), 7.18–7.5 (3H, m, CH and ArH), 7.5–7.84 (2H, m, ArH), 7.9–8.24 (4H, m, ArH), 11.29 (1H, br s, NH); **e** (61%), 148–49°; ν_{\max} 3125, 1770, 1705, 1600, 1580 cm⁻¹; δ 3.82 (3H, s, OCH₃), 4.26 (2H, d, CH₂), 6.92 (2H, d, ArH), 7.26 (1H, t, CH), 7.45 (2H, d, ArH), 7.76–8.04 (4H, m, ArH), 11.32 (1H, s, NH); **f** (75%), 167–69°; ν_{\max} 3185, 1770, 1715, 1590, 1510 cm⁻¹; δ 3.72 (3H, s, OCH₃), 3.82 (3H, s, OCH₃), 4.3 (2H, d, CH₂), 6.8–7.24 (3H, m, ArH), 7.32 (1H, t, CH), 7.84–8.08 (4H, m, ArH), 11.1 (1H, s, NH); **g** (80%), 171–73°; ν_{\max} 3330, 3100, 1770, 1720, 1675, 1590, 1530 cm⁻¹; δ 2.12 (3H, s, COCH₃), 4.3 (2H, d, CH₂), 7.28 (1H, t, CH), 7.38–7.8 (4H, m, ArH),

7.86–8.32 (4H, m, ArH), 10.32 (1H, s, NH), 11.12 (1H, s, NH); **h** (68%), 158–60°; ν_{\max} 3205, 1770, 1715, 1610, 1530 cm⁻¹; δ 4.29 (2H, d, CH₂), 7.36 (1H, t, CH), 7.7–8.14 (6H, m, ArH), 8.36 (1H, s, ArH), 8.52 (1H, d, ArH), 11.54 (1H, br s, ArH); **i** (63%), 129–31°; ν_{\max} 3520, 3450, 1775, 1710 cm⁻¹; δ 4.28 (2H, d, CH₂), 7.32 (1H, t, CH), 7.44–8.46 (11H, m, ArH), 11.4 (1H, br s, NH); **j** (95%), 167–69°; ν_{\max} 3140, 1770, 1700 cm⁻¹; δ 2.84 (3H, s, CH₃), 4.4 (2H, d, CH₂), 7.38 (1H, t, CH), 7.76–8.08 (4H, m, ArH), 10.8 (1H, s, NH); all compounds, λ_{\max} 218–220 nm.

Antitumor screening: The antitumor screening of the compounds was carried out at the National Cancer Institute (NCI), USA, according to their recent protocol. Each compound was tested at 5 different concentrations against 60 cell lines of 8 types of human cancers as leukemia, lung (non-small cell and small cell), colon, CNS, melanoma, ovarian and renal cancers. The *in vitro* effects of the compounds on the viability of EAC cells were also evaluated. Thus different doses of compounds dissolved in sterile dimethyl sulphoxide (0.1 ml) were added to EAC cell suspensions in physiological saline (0.9 ml) containing 10⁶ cells/ml to give final drug concentrations of 2.0, 1.5 and 1.0 μ mol ml⁻¹ respectively, with the control receiving 0.1 ml of DMSO in equal total volume. After incubation at 37° for 2 h, total number of viable cells were counted by trypan blue dye exclusion test, the result being expressed in percentage of dead cells.

Anti-HIV screening: All the compounds were screened for their anti-HIV activity at NCI, USA, according to standard procedure⁸. The candidate compound was dissolved in DMSO then diluted 1 : 100 in cell culture medium before preparing serial half-log₁₀ dilutions. T4 lymphocytes (CEM cell line) were added and after a brief interval HIV-1 was added, resulting in a 1 : 200 final dilution of the compound. Uninfected cells with the compound served as a toxicity control and infected and uninfected cells without the compound served as basic controls. The cultures were then incubated at 37° in a 5% carbon dioxide atmosphere for 6 days. The tetrazolium salt XTT [{2,3-bis(2-methoxy-4-nitro-5-sulphophenyl)-2H-tetrazolium-5-carboxanilide} sodium salt] was added to all wells and cultures were incubated to develop formazan colour by viable cells. Then the individual wells were analysed spectrophotometrically and also observed microscopically for detection of viable cells and confirmation of protective activity. Drug-treated virus-infected cells were compared with drug-treated non-infected cells and with other appropriate controls (untreated infected and untreated noninfected cells, drug-containing wells without cells etc.) on the same plate. Data were reviewed in comparison with other tests done at the same time and a determination about the activity was made. All tests were compared with positive control [AZT

(3'-azido-3'-deoxythymidine)-treated] done at the same time under identical conditions.

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